

THE ROLE OF FREE WIRELESS FIDELITY (WI-FI) SERVICE, FOOD QUALITY, AND SERVICESCAPE TOWARD CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Rizal Ula Ananta Fauzi ^{1*}

¹Management Study Program Faculty of Economics & Business University of PGRI Madiun, Indonesia

*Corresponding author, rizalmanajemen@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Culinary tourism is still one of the people's choices in Indonesia. Many culinary businesses field requires competitive strategies to get an edge. The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of Free Wireless Fidelity (Wifi) services, Food Quality and ServiceScape toward Customer Satisfaction. This research was conducted in 4 cafes in Madiun with a sample of 125 respondents. We use multiple regression statistical analyses were performed in this study. The research indicates that the Free Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi) Service and Servicescape have a positive influence on Customer Satisfaction. While food quality has no effect on customer satisfaction in Madiun Cafe. Consumers prefer the service and atmosphere provided rather than the type of food offered by the café. so that it can be considered by businesses to determine marketing strategies to satisfy consumers.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction Food Quality, Free Wireless Fidelity, Servicescape

INTRODUCTION

Based on data from the central statistical agency shown that Economic growth in Madiun is 6.03 percent. Some creative economic businesses dominated in three sectors namely culinary 67.66 percent, fashion 15.00 percent, and crafts 14.56 percent and other creative sectors only 2.77 percent. Culinary, who are rich in food menus, has become a trend of Indonesian people. Madiun is an area in eastern Java that presents a variety of tourism and culinary potential. Starting from the roadside angkringan to the café which offers a variety of services ranging from attractive room decor, free wifi services and a variety of foods offered. From the many services offered by researchers, we want to see the dominant factors that influence consumer satisfaction in the selection of cafes. This is expected to keep its business consistent and able to increase the culinary business turnover.

There are 10 cafes in Madiun that have become recommendations and choices for consumers, especially teenagers. Of the 10 cafes in Madiun, researchers focused on 4 cafes namely, Prague Coffee & Eatery, Waroeng Om Breng, angkringan rute 57, and Warung Lantera. Election 4 cafes in Madiun, because the cafe is the most crowded visited by consumers. Each trader tries to present the best menu, best services, and facilities to meet customer satisfaction. Satisfaction is

an impression of hope. Consumers will feel satisfied if the service performances exceed customer expectations. Once consumers satisfied with the goods and services, they will back again to repurchase. Guiltinan *et al.* (1997) the role of customer satisfaction can increase customer loyalty. A business will get more profit and dominate the market if the seller can provide customer satisfaction. Consumer satisfaction has a relationship with the quality of the products offered by the seller.

The best quality of service given will increase customer satisfaction. Free Wi-Fi service is one of the choices of consumers in choosing cafes, especially young people to get a free internet network, a generation of digitization that makes young people not separated from the internet either for just chatting, watching videos looking for news information or to support doing their tasks.

Besides Wi-Fi service, the quality of food offered can influence customer satisfaction. Good products and services will affect the level of customer satisfaction, and if the seller doesn't pay attention to the product and service, the level of customer satisfaction will be bad. Consumers are the parties who play an important role in assessing the quality of products offered. The atmosphere with nice and unique decor is one of the customer's choices. The menu chosen by customers can be influenced by the situation and context (Meiselman, 1996). the purpose of this study was to see the role of free wireless fidelity (wi-fi) service, food quality and services cape toward customer satisfaction. then as a consideration determining business strategies to increase customer satisfaction because customer satisfaction is a business goal to win the competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONSUMER SATISFACTION

Customer satisfaction is the consumer assessment of overall product performance toward expectations (Anderson and Sullivan 1993). According to Kotler (2009), Satisfaction is a feeling of hate or like. Jasfar (2005) comparison between perceptions of services received. Yamit (2013) Several ways to satisfy customers can be done by finding information about customer needs, looking for information about the purchasing decision process and building company reputation.

WIRELESS FIDELITY SERVICE

Wi-Fi stands for Wireless Fidelity, is a medium for communicating wireless data and is used as a fast communication tool. (Wi-Fi) only works if the device is connected to the network (Priyambodo, 2005). (Wi-Fi)Benefits are network connectivity to find information checking e-mail, relationships with colleagues and accessing various applications (Geier, 2005: 26). Customers are looking for an internet connection because to reduce internet data packages purchasing on mobile or mobile applications. So customer expectations are not only to find a meal menu but also do the work and find the information they need. A fast and uninterrupted Wi-Fi network connection offered by the cafe is a choice and convenience for customers in finding the information they need. Fauzi's research (2017) free Wi-Fi has a significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions. Internet connection provided is one of the services that influence customer satisfaction (Antonio, *et al.* 2018 and Hamilton *et al.* 2017). Then researchers hypothesized

H1: there is the effect of free Wi-Fi service on customer satisfaction.

FOOD QUALITY

Product quality is a customer's assessment of total product excellence (Anselmsson et al., 2007). (Baker et al., 2002 and Kim et al., 2004) Food quality is an important factor in customer satisfaction. Preparing a product that has the best quality is a must for entrepreneurs. The better the quality of the products offered by the seller, the higher the level of customer satisfaction. The quality of a food menu product is very important and must be considered for every culinary founder. Kotler (2000) Quality is a characteristic of a product or service that matches real capabilities. Qin et.al (2010) state that the quality of the waiter influences consumer satisfaction. Namkung and Jang (2007) the influence of food quality on customer satisfaction and consumer intentions. Taste and health, which are most important for product choices (Ophuis and Van Trijp, 1995). Rashid et al. (2016) states that food quality affects consumer satisfaction. therefore

H2 food quality affects customer satisfaction.

SERVICESCAPE

Servicescape is a customer experience related to the service environment (Harris and Ezeh, 2008). Bitner (1992) the total dimensions of the environment. Pangkey (2013) physical facilities of a company to influence feelings. Countryman and Jang (2006) physical facilities offered. A unique, comfortable environment with the characteristics displayed will create one's emotions. The nature of services cape is related to service and atmosphere. (Hoffman and Turley, 2002; Kotler, 1973) Lovelock and Wirtz (2011) physical appearance styles encountered by customers through the impressions received by the five senses can create customer satisfaction. Bitner (1992) Ransulangi et al, (2015) services cape significantly influence consumer satisfaction. Hypothesis built

H3. *Servicescape affect customer satisfaction*

METHODOLOGY

This research is explanatory research with a quantitative approach. The population in this study is a consumer of four cafes located in Madiun. Because the number of consumers is unknown, so the researchers used the Maholthra (2006) formula by multiplying 4 or 5 question items. In this study there were 25 question items, so the number of samples taken was 125 samples. From 125 samples taken by division as follows:

Table 1. Respondents

No	Name of café	Numer of samples	Number of samples
1	prague coffe,e &eatery,		31
2	waroeng om bring		31
3	angkringan rute 57,		31
4	warung lantera.		32
	Total		125

The questionnaire was given to consumers who were in 4 cafes in table 1. Data taken by giving questionnaires to respondents using a Likert scale of 1 to 5. Number 1 states strongly disagree with number 5 which states strongly agree.

In this study, the research concept that was built was the effect of Free Wi-Fi Service, food quality and Servicescape on customer satisfaction.

Picture 1. Schematic of free Wi-Fi influence, food quality, services cape toward customer satisfaction

MEASUREMENT

Levesque and MacDougall (1996). To measure satisfaction used. The right choice, suitability of expectations, and satisfaction. Gye-Soo (2007) measures satisfaction with services, responses, processes, and benefits received by consumers. Al-Shafi, S. (2008) to measure the quality of Free Wifi services with the use, benefits, security, and speed of the network. To measure food quality with Heide and Olsen (2018), taste, quality, health, and nutrition. Bitner (1992), Zeithaml et al., (2006). Several aspects of viewing servicescape are (1) symbols and artifacts. (2) decoration and design interior (3) atmosphere and song.

The research model measurement for this study was tested using SPSS Version 23.0. The procedure shows that the SPSS analysis consists of two steps: The first measure is the validity test and the reliability test questionnaire. Validity Test is used to measure the validity of the questionnaire statement, a good statement fulfills validity and is said to be valid if the correlation r value $> 0,3$. While the questionnaire reliability test was conducted to measure the consistency of the questionnaire given to respondents. A questionnaire is said to be reliability if Cronbach's alpha value $> 0,6$ (Sugiono, 2013). The second step is regression analysis to answer the hypothesis. partial effect. between the independent variables consisting of free wifi, food quality and Servicescape services on the dependent variable, namely customer satisfaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of calculating the correlation using SPSS are obtained by the data in table 2.

Table 2. Questionnaire Measurements

Variable	R-value	Cronbach's alpha
Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi) service		
Customers often use free wifi service in cafes	0,7635	0.821
Customers often experience obstacles in free wifi services	0,5167	0.847
Using free wifi is easy for customers	0,5952	0.824
Overall, customers get the convenience of free wifi	0,5243	0.793
Using the free wifi service was able to complete my task	0,6543	0.778
Wifi service is very useful for customers	0,4708	0.770

Overall free wifi services benefit consumers.	0,5802	0.813
Consumers feel safe in sending information	0,7297	0.814
Consumers feel the connection speed in the free wifi service	0,5331	0.864
Food quality		
The cafe has a good taste	0,7961	0.754
The cafe has good food quality	0,7412	0.743
The cafe has a good healthy meal	0,7412	0.726
The cafe has a good quality of nutrition meal	0,6713	0.776
Servicescape		
Good attractive facilities	0,5372	0.824
Waiters wear good clothes	0,7074	0.840
high standard of service quality	0,5443	0.836
The great decoration to attract customers	0,4218	0.794
The picture on the wall attracts customers	0,4459	0.848
Great Furnishings	0,5097	0.810
Accompanied by life music	0,6970	0.806
Customer Satisfaction		
I feel satisfaction with the cafe service	0,5777	0.709
I feel satisfied with the service process	0,6562	0.810
I feel satisfied with the response given	0,6065	0.736
I feel more benefits	0,4790	0.744
Overall I am satisfied with this cafe.	0,4169	0.735

Source : the results of the data are processed SPSS

To measure the validity of a questionnaire, the data is said to be valid if r value is greater than 0.3 while the data is said reliability to be greater than 0.6. The results of validity and reliability measurements.

Table 3. Anova

	Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.494	3	1.831	26.080	.000 ^a
	Residual	8.497	121	.070		
	Total	13.991	124			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Servicescape, quality food, free Wi-Fi

b. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction

Source: the results of the data are processed SPSS

Multiple regression analysis using the F (Fisher) test aims to determine the effect of all research variables together which include: Free Wi-Fi, Quality food, Servicescape has a positive effect on customer satisfaction at Madiun Café. From the test results obtained the calculated F value of 26,080 with a significance of $0,000 > 0,05$, it can be concluded that Free Wi-Fi, Quality food, Servicescape together have a positive effect on customer satisfaction in Madiun Cafe.

Table 4. coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Beta			
1	Constant	1.928	.235		8.216	.000
	Free Wi-Fi	.198	.070	.285	2.839	.005
	Quality food	-.045	.056	-.079	-.797	.427
	Servicescape	.398	.065	.493	6.129	.000

Source: the results of the data are processed SPSS

Based on the table above, the regression equations formed in this regression test are:

$$Y = 1.928 + 0.198X_1 - 0.045X_2 + 0.398X_3$$

From the equation above can be seen that a constant value of 1,928 can be interpreted if the Free Wi-Fi Service, Product Quality and Servicescape variables are considered with no change, then customer satisfaction in Madiun cafe will remain at 1,928. the Free Wi-Fi Service variable of 0.198 has a positive meaning if the perception toward the Free Wi-Fi Service is getting better, then customer satisfaction will increase. Food quality of -.045 has a negative meaning if perceptions of food quality are improved, so it will not affect the level of customer satisfaction. While the value of Servicescape of 0.398 has a positive value means if the perception of Servicescape is better, customer satisfaction will increase.

The results of the study showed that the quality value of free Wi-fi <0.05 so that the quality of free Wi-Fi influences customer satisfaction. This is consistent with the hypothesis that the free Wi-Fi service influences customer satisfaction. Research Antonio, et al 2018 and Hamilton et. al 2017) states that the internet connection provided can give satisfaction effect on consumers. Consumers feel satisfaction because the services received by customers in accessing the internet support the users with the need for fast internet access and rarely troubles. This makes free Wifi quality service satisfying customers in Madiun cafes. The average customer needs an internet connection in their activities.

The results of the study obtained a significance value of food > 0.05 so that the quality of food does not affect customer satisfaction. This is supported by research by Liu et.al (2019) saying that food quality does not affect consumer satisfaction because good food quality will provide comparable expensive prices. food quality studies alone are not enough to guarantee consumer satisfaction, but also consider the role of prices (Gneezy et al., 2014). This is not following the hypothesis that food quality has an influence on consumer satisfaction and research Rashid (2016) which states that food quality affects consumer satisfaction Teen customers pay less attention to food quality because they are more inclined to the quality of the free Wi-Fi they need and also the good atmosphere. This means that the café available in Madison is not only for the main purpose of selling food menus but rather for more purposes as a place and facility for customers to find Wi-Fi and a comfortable place supported by the availability of food menus.

In this research, services cape get a significance value <0.05 so that services cape affects customer satisfaction. Servicescape in business creates attractive images and results in better

services (Barich and Kotler, 1991). This is consistent with the hypothesis which states that Servicescape influences customer satisfaction. Research by Mary Jo Bitner (1992) Ransulangi, et al, (2015) found evidence that services cape had a significant effect on customer satisfaction. A sense of comfort is the choice of consumers because of their social-emotional and as a background for taking selfies photos, which is a trend among young people.

The results of this research can be used as input for entrepreneurs and prospective culinary entrepreneurs with the target consumers of teenagers in particular in the city of Madiun, that Pree Wi-Fi service facilities and services cape become the choice of adolescents compared to food quality, business people can do the right strategy for keep developing the business and advancing its business. The development of technology that continues to evolve to change people's behavior and community needs. Internet connection is a necessity that cannot be separated from the lives of today's teenagers. The distribution of profile photos and selfies on social media makes good Servicescape a choice.

CONCLUSIONS

Basically, the purpose of business is to create customer satisfaction. Various strategies business people do to create satisfaction. Including providing free Wi-Fi services and creating an attractive room atmosphere decoration. The benefits of satisfaction provide the benefits of maintaining relationships between consumers and business people. Positive interactions that are built will create customer satisfaction. (Kwortnik, 2008). Young people go to the main destination cafe not because they are looking for food but because they are looking for a comfortable place and a smooth and easy internet connection. This can be an income for entrepreneurs and prospective culinary entrepreneurs for young consumers the need for internet networks and the environment makes it a priority choice. The limitations of this study were carried out in East Java in Indonesia. For further researchers, the population taken can be larger and adds variable prices that affect consumer satisfaction.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

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